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Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development in Connection with Technology-Enhanced Learning Environments

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ABSTRACT

Technology-enhanced learning environments (TELEs) that support social interaction between teachers and learners are common in engineering higher education institutes. TELEs are often equipped with professional hardware and software, which not only enable learners to gain access to variety of learning instruments, but also allow learners to practice with authentic equipment and design tools. Furthermore, teachers can use TELEs and scaffolding principles to organize teaching in several ways that are beyond traditional classrooms. This paper discusses the potential of TELEs to shape the zone of proximal development (ZPD) of learners such that they could do harder learning activities than would otherwise be possible in less conducive environments. In addition, an example of a conducive TELE is presented that might have enlarged ZPD of learners, and, as such, may partly explain good learning outcomes obtained. The illustrations in this paper may help teachers to gain better understanding of the benefits of environment creation as well as to organize learning episodes that are suitable for ZPD-based thinking.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Sustainability and Engineering Education, Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning

Keywords: Zone of Proximal Development, Scaffolding, Technology-Enhanced Learning Environments, Engineering Education

INTRODUCTION

The concept of zone of proximal development (ZPD) belongs to Vygotsky's sociocultural theory of learning that enable teachers to understand learning processes through conscious intellectual activity in social settings. The paradigm of ZPD is that learners are more capable with the help of a more competent peer or teacher than they could be alone. In principle, teachers should challenge learners with tasks they cannot completely do on their own; rather teachers should provide just enough assistance such that learners are finally able to complete the tasks independently. Such an assistance process is known as *scaffolding* [1]. In general,

scaffolding can be built in various ways; for example, by contact teaching, personal advice, peer interactions or feedback, which all share social dimension. In contrast, learning materials and activities not involving human interactions such as video clips, virtual laboratories, games and other software can also be understood as scaffolds that help learners to complete specific steps of some complex task. Please refer e.g., to [2–4] for more information on software-based scaffolds. Nonetheless, teachers should design and assign learning activities within ZPD of learners, set up environments that are conducive for those activities, and use scaffolding in order to enable high learning gains.

Currently, universities invest in technology-enhanced learning environments (TELEs), which are equipped with ancillaries such as modern web-technologies, audiovisual hardware, and professional software. Furthermore, construction and furniture layout of these environments are usually organized such that group-work and social interaction between teachers and learners are readily enabled. Therefore, TELEs are believed to provide better support for various teaching methods, enhance flexibility of learning, and favor authentic learning activities to be conducted compared with traditional classrooms. Furthermore, TELEs also enable natural support for social scaffolding processes and even for tailoring specific scaffolds for specific learning activities. Hence, it is justifiable to link the concept of ZPD of learners with TELEs, and to investigate TELEs' potential to enlarge the notional size of ZPD of learners. As such, this paper applies diagrammatic reasoning like in [5], in order to illustrate Vygotsky's ZPD in connection with TELEs.

The main contributions of this paper are: 1) to illustrate that TELEs have potential to shape ZPD of learners, and 2) to present an example of a TELE with selected scaffolds that have been set up for particular educational objectives intended to bachelor's level engineering students. The illustrations and examples in this paper may help teachers to harness TELEs and scaffolding principles for the benefit of learning. They may also help teachers to design and organize learning episodes that are suitable for ZPD-based way of thinking. At best, pedagogical scripting and scaffolding connected with TELEs may actually enlarge ZPD of learners, which is an important standpoint for any educational activity, as it would generally allow higher level tasks to be completed by learners. The scientific contribution of this paper is perhaps not limited to engineering higher education only. The discussion is presumably general enough so that other educational disciplines may benefit as well.

1 ZONE OF PROXIMAL DEVELOPMENT AND PRINCIPLE OF SCAFFOLDING

The ZPD describes set of learning activities that individual learners cannot do only by themselves, but which they can complete with scaffolding. According to Vygotsky [6], the set of such learning activities can be defined as “the distance between the actual development level, as determined by independent problem solving, and the level of potential development, as determined through problem solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers”. The ZPD and scaffolding along with an appropriately assigned learning activity are illustrated in *Fig. 1*.

Initially in *Fig. 1*, the learning activity is beyond learner's independent abilities, that is, before scaffolding has taken place. After successful scaffolding, learner is ready to complete the learning activity using his own abilities without help from scaffolds. The fictitious boundary of ZPD therefore defines new limits for the zone of current development (ZCD), which defines the set of learning activities that learner is able to do unaided. Updated ZCD maps individual development process and it makes learner more receptive for higher-level activities.

Fig. 1. A learning activity (diamond) is initially beyond learner's independent abilities. After teaching, scaffolding is removed and learner is ready to complete the activity using his own abilities. The boundary of ZPD defines the limits for the updated ZCD.

In this sense, *Fig. 1* clarifies the necessity of teaching: teaching attempts to make learners to do more, and it helps learners to surpass their current abilities. *Fig. 1* also emphasizes the nature of activities that should be assigned to learners: Teachers should assign activities that learners are unable to accomplish themselves, but which they can do with guidance [5]. Furthermore, the learning activity gets harder when it is placed near the outer boundary of ZPD, and easier, if it is moved towards ZCD.

In [5], Wass & Golding have recommended that harder tasks will lead to improved learning. Hence, attributes such as knowledge base, mastery of substance, pedagogical scripting skills, and even courage of teachers do play an important role when learning activities are placed near the outer limits of ZPD of learners. It is also crucial that sufficient prerequisites of students are ensured. Nonetheless, it should be noted that each learner do hold different abilities, and hence, individual ZPDs and ZCDs differs between learners. Furthermore, individual learners generally require unequal timely investment for completion of learning activities. Taking this viewpoint, the quality of students, their current knowledge level, abilities, and regulation skills limit the level of learning activities that can be assigned without e.g., cognitive overload and making things too difficult for students to handle under a sensible timespan.

2 LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AND LEVEL OF POTENTIAL DEVELOPMENT

In [5], Wass & Golding have proposed that changes in teaching environment change ZPD of learners. Specifically, they believe that learning environments that are targeted for particular learning activities can enlarge ZPD of learners, and, as a result, would allow learners to complete harder tasks compared with less conducive environments. Such a claim is relatively strong, but it is also very significant, because learning gains could be improved by focusing on environment creation. The extended ZPD of learners, i.e. the increased level of potential development enabled by a conducive learning environment is depicted in *Fig. 2*.

However, Wass & Golding mostly focus on the role of social environment, where active engagement and sustained discussion between students and teachers occur, and where prompt feedback is given to students. They also put emphasis on the learning activities occurring within the environments e.g., critical evaluation tasks versus rote learning and factual recall. Undoubtedly, their claims and examples are convincing and trustworthy.

Fig. 2. Learning environment B is more conducive for particular learning activities compared with environment A. Harder tasks can be completed in B than in A. Environment B therefore increases the level of potential development of learners.

Yet, neither theoretical studies nor empirical research has been focused on the potential of physical or virtual environments to shape ZPD of learners. Shaping ZPD of learners essentially means that learners' abilities to complete learning activities through *scaffolding* are changed, and that change, in this case, must be linked to the scaffolding process itself. In addition to teacher's direct actions and social interaction, technology-mediated ancillaries offered by the TELEs can further strengthen scaffolding processes. Hence, it is justifiable to link scaffold-supporting features of these ancillaries to the notional size of ZPD of learners. The activity viewpoint as described in *Fig. 1* and *Fig. 2* is especially useful for such a purpose.

It is important to note that TELEs are commonly found in educational institutes throughout the world; especially in engineering higher education institutes. An example of a modern TELE is depicted in *Fig. 3*, which potentially resembles environment B in *Fig. 2*.

Fig. 3. A cell-oriented configurable TELE that supports varying group sizes. Each desk is movable and consists of two workstations and individual PCs. Desks can be attached together to form larger consoles. The whole TELE can be divided up to 4 separate cells, and each cell have an own large movable display, which is accessible from any PC. All PCs are equipped with professional engineering software, and have quick access to online library and other learning resources. [7]

In what follows, an example of a conducive TELE that have been set up for particular learning activities is presented; namely, a miniature process environment for flexible learning and open-ended engineering design. Better learning outcomes have been obtained since the fabrication of the pilot environment compared with earlier approaches by monitoring the performance of a batch of 50 engineering students.

Nonetheless, students have generally performed better: They have been able to solve more advanced and more difficult problems than before. They have shown critical thinking, even as regards to their own work. They have compared and contrasted their work with their peers. They have invented new strategies for solving engineering design tasks, and to some extent, have been more satisfied and happier than before.

However, scientific reasoning for such improvements is still somewhat unclear, and hence, the diagrammatic framework of ZPD and scaffolding as in *Fig. 1* and *Fig. 2* is selected to provide new insights to the relation between scaffolding and learning. Partially, the improvements have come at a price e.g., by necessity for goal orientation and sustained engagement, which require regulation skills and increased timely investment for completion of learning activities. Some students have been uncomfortable with such features and slight avoidance has been observed. It also seems that well-performing students perform even better, while others underachieve. Social cognitive theory and self-efficacy may partly explain the avoidance behavior.

3 EXAMPLE: MINIATURE PROCESS ENVIRONMENT FOR FLEXIBLE LEARNING AND OPEN-ENDED ENGINEERING DESIGN

Miniature demo processes that are small-scale versions of industry-scale processes are trending in engineering education. Some of them have fixed structure; some have additional freedom of configuration. Miniature processes benefit both teachers and learners. For example, teachers can easily bring them inside classrooms, and use them to illustrate physical phenomena, and to show real-time technical demos to students. Teachers can also set up environments in which several different miniature processes are simultaneously installed. Depending on room design and regulations, students can be allowed to have relatively free access there, practice open-ended engineering, and make use of science for the benefit of their own learning. Better access enhances flexibility of learning, while open-endedness provide alternate ways to understand lecture notes and other course material. Open-endedness also enables students to discover new things in science with their own volition.

An example of a certain workstation from such an environment is depicted in *Fig. 4*. The miniature process in the right-hand side of *Fig. 4* is a rotating DC-motor that can be supplemented by two different attachments; namely, by a rotating disc attachment and by an inverted pendulum. The disc can be used to understand rotary motion as well as to investigate position and velocity control, which both are widespread in different areas of technology. The inverted pendulum on the other hand can be used to learn balance control, which is relative common e.g., in mobile robots. Furthermore, software-based virtual laboratory environments, or simulators, can relatively easily be created to supplement device level equipment. An example of such an environment is MathWorks Matlab/Simulink software, where students can do e.g., model-based design before working with the physical device. These virtual environments can be constructed using block diagrams that show causal connections between each physical instrument. They are also able to quickly produce comparable results as the real equipment does. Interested readers may refer e.g., to [8] for more examples on pedagogical use of virtual laboratory environments.

Fig. 4. Workstation of process environment (left) and miniature DC-motor (right).

In what follows, an example of a thoughtfully scripted learning episode that is executed in the miniature process environment is briefly discussed. The rotating DC-motor of *Fig. 4* is adopted as an example device. The episode is broken into three separate phases that have specific ZPD-based educational purposes.

Phase 1: Student groups are first given a teacher-made but only partly completed simulator that is based on the mathematical model of the physical DC-motor. The parameters of the model are available in the manufacturer's datasheets, and students are required to browse through the datasheets and complete the model. After completion of the model, students need to do several preselected simulation tasks that help them to understand the dynamic characteristics of the system.

Phase 2: Student groups need to pick a topic from several different alternatives available e.g., position control of a rotary disc attachment. Students are also given a set of standard design constraints and requirements that must be fulfilled using the simulator before working with the physical device. For the most active students, the simulator allows them to freely carry out open-ended engineering design e.g., by trying different theoretical methods and learn from the experience. In addition, there are number of different approaches available in each topic that can potentially yield good results. It is left for students to find a reasonable approach, and justify their choices. Finally, an experimental result from the manufacturer is provided to students for benchmarking purposes.

Phase 3: When students have satisfied all design constraints and requirements, they are ready for the actual experiments. The tests are carried out such that three groups are present at the same time. The purpose of such a choice is that students see different design approaches of different topics and their rationale. Hence, they can learn from other groups as well, which allow them to weigh their own design with others. More importantly, teacher provides short and personalized microteaching during the testing phase, which strengthens students' understanding. Microteaching in this case provides specific support for specific tasks, and it allows prompt feedback to be delivered to each student groups, and even to individual students.

The simulator in Phase 1 makes students familiar with the operation principles of the given physical system. Furthermore, datasheet browsing helps students to understand how essential information is commonly shared through them. The preselected simulation tasks predict dynamic behaviour of the real equipment, and enable students to virtually observe several quantities that cannot be displayed by the physical instruments. The simulations not only demonstrate the benefits of

software-based design in terms of general engineering work: access, time-scale, prediction, data-analysis, etc., but they also illustrate limitations of virtuality e.g., model uncertainties and other sources of error. Therefore, the virtual simulation environment works as a software-based scaffold that aims to enlarge ZPD of learners by surpassing the limitations of physical environment, and by offering much faster information retrieval compared with physical devices.

The requirements in Phase 2 problematize students' work and draw their attention to issues that might otherwise be overlooked. More importantly, the requirements make students to do sustainable, reliable and safe engineering design, which serve them in the long run. That is, the list of requirements is one of the key scaffolds that enable students to do successful work.

Phase 2 is also the point when students face engineering challenge: they must seek relevant literature and find potential solution candidates for their own topic. Often, students must do some trial-and-error experiments as well, which actually strengthens their knowledge level, because they learn characteristics of the chosen candidate. Students must also weigh the pros and cons of the candidates, and hence, they understand why some candidates work better than others do. Through this process, students learn important features of engineering science, research and practice, as well as the phases of work and design, and the iterative nature of project working, which all prepares them to face engineering challenges in the future. In addition, the benchmark result gives a challenging reference for students to see what kind of performance is roughly expected. For most of the students, the benchmark result seems to be a driving force towards better engineering. Furthermore, many student seem to understand that good results are not easily achieved, and hence, effort, timely investment, teamwork and help seeking are required in order to reach meaningful learning objectives.

Finally, Phase 3 allows students to see their own design in action. Because there are several groups simultaneously present, students can share their knowledge to their peers, discuss about them, and possibly use help from the teacher ('the more capable peer') to support their findings, or to provide additional information. That is, Phase 3 focus entirely on improving the social dimension of learning compared with strictly teacher-led instruction, and thereby, aims to enlarge ZPD of learners through social scaffolding process in a supporting environment.

Students have been surprisingly satisfied with the social scaffolding process delivered by the teacher at the end of Phase 3, and with the technological ancillaries within the TELE. According to student feedback, many felt that these kind of learning episodes with task diversification, technological learning instruments as well as with active social interaction between students and teachers have substantially helped their personal learning and development processes, and, as a result, they have expressed willingness to learn more by co-creation of authentic problem solving. It also seems that students get fascinated when they see the outcome of their own design in real-time, which tend to increase motivation towards completion of learning activities.

In summary, it is justifiable to believe that the created TELE enable learners to work with hard authentic learning activities that are placed as in the right-hand side of *Fig. 2*, and hence, scaffolds students to reach high-level educational objectives otherwise out of reach. Therefore, the fabricated miniature process environment might resemble that of environment B in *Fig. 2*, but more experiences need to be gained to make implications that are more representative.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The possibility of technology-enhanced learning environments (TELEs) to increase the level of potential development of learners was discussed in this paper. The level of potential development was identified with Vygotsky's zone of proximal development (ZPD) and with the notion of scaffolding. Diagrammatic reasoning was used to illustrate that TELEs may enlarge ZPD of learners, and, as a result, would allow high-level academic activities to be completed by learners. The key argument in this case is that TELEs and their ancillaries may strengthen scaffolding processes, which translate to better learning outcomes. Furthermore, an example of a conducive TELE along with specifically designed scaffolds were shortly presented that support ZPD-based teaching practice and claims in this paper. The scientific contribution of this paper may help teachers to gain new insights for the scaffolding potential of TELEs, and to use environment creation for the benefit of learning.

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